

FULL-FIELD PULSE-ECHO ULTRASONIC WAVE PROPAGATION IMAGING FOR NONDESTRUCTIVE COMPOSITE INSPECTION

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ABSTRACT

Composite structures have an advantage of weight to strength ratio compared with metallic materials, such as carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) and glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP), which is extensively applied to various industries. However, failure mechanism of composite structures is more complex than metallic structures and thus the defect detection in composite structures is also more difficult. C-scan, one of inspection results based on through transmission ultrasound in nondestructive ultrasonic testing, shows an excellent result detecting defects such as delamination and debonding which are invisible in composite structures. Conventional C-scan systems have usually used the couplants like gel, water injection and water-immersion. However, the conventional C-scan method has the limitation of stand-off distance between transducer and structure and the fixed single frequency transducer. Recently, laser ultrasonic generator is widely used as a non-contact nondestructive inspection tool because it generates broadband ultrasound on the structure based on thermoelastic mechanism. In addition, sensing laser as a non-contact sensor is used to measure the ultrasound of various modes on the surface and through-the-thickness directions of a structure. In this study, full-field pulse-echo ultrasonic wave propagation imaging (UWPI) for nondestructive composite inspection visualizes the defects induced in composite structures. For composite inspection, the full-field pulse-echo ultrasonic propagation imaging (UPI) system using generation and sensing lasers with two-axis linear translation stage was used to inspect defects in composite structures which are CFRP wing skin panel, GFRP aircraft encoder case and Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) pipe.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite structures have an advantage of weight to strength ratio compared with metallic structures, such as CFRP and GFRP, which is extensively applied to various industries. However, fracture mechanism of composite structures is more complex than metallic structures. Thus, the defect detection in composite structures is difficult. C-scan, one of inspection results based on through-the-thickness ultrasound in nondestructive ultrasonic testing, shows an excellent result detecting defects such as delamination and debonding which are invisible in composite structures. Conventional C-scan systems have usually used a non-contact inspection method, such as air-coupled ultrasonic transducer with the couplant or water. However, the conventional C-scan methods have the limitation of stand-off distance between transducer and structure and the fixed single frequency transducer. Recently, laser ultrasonic generator is widely used as a non-contact nondestructive inspection tool [1] because it generates ultrasound of diverse modes throughout broadband by thermoelastic mechanism on the surface of structures [2]. In addition, many researchers are interested in non-contact sensing method due to the advantage of accessibility compared to contact sensing. Laser is one of non-contact sensing methods to measure ultrasound or vibration in structures. Generally, sensing laser measures broadband

ultrasound or vibration from a few meters to tens of meters.

In this study, composites structures were inspected using full-field pulse-echo ultrasonic wave propagation imaging (UWPI) technique to visualize the defects in composite structures. For nondestructive composite inspection, full-field pulse-echo ultrasonic propagation imaging (UPI) system was configured with a laser ultrasonic generator and a sensing laser with a two-axis linear translation system based on pulse-echo inspection method. A CFRP wing skin panel, a GFRP aircraft encoder case and a PVC pipe structure including defects were inspected using full-field UPI system and the defects were visualized based on full-field pulse-echo UWPI technique.

2 MECHANISM OF FULL-FIELD PULSE-ECHO ULTRASONIC PROPAGATION IMAGING SYSTEM FOR NONDESTRUCTIVE COMPOSITE INSPECTION

In order to inspect non-destructively composite structures, full-field pulse-echo ultrasonic propagation imaging (UPI) system was used as shown in Fig. 1a. The two laser beams scan composite structures along raster scanning pattern based on two-axis linear translation stage. As shown in Fig. 1b, the Q-switched laser generates diverse mode ultrasounds like bulk wave through the thickness and Lamb wave or surface wave in plane by thermoelastic mechanism. The sensing laser can capture pulse-echo through-the-thickness ultrasound by impinging the sensing laser beam at the same point as the generation laser beam. This sensing principle is repeated over the scan area and thus a full-field ultrasound as large as the scan area can be visualized by the UWPI algorithm.

Figure 1: Full-field pulse-echo UPI system: (a) concept, and (b) mechanism.

As a result of scan using full-field pulse-echo UPI system, full-field pulse-echo UWPI is generated to visualize defects in composite structures based on acquired through-the-thickness ultrasound signals in scan area based on full-field pulse-echo UWPI technique. The one dimensional through-the-thickness ultrasound signals in the composite structure are arranged to three dimensional array as shown in Fig. 2. After that, full-field pulse-echo UWPI movie is generated along to propagation direction of through-the-thickness ultrasound and the defects in the composite structure are visualized and evaluated by full-field pulse-echo UWPI freeze frame snapshots.

Figure 2: Full-field pulse-echo ultrasonic wave propagation imaging algorithm.

3 NONDESTRUCTIVE COMPOSITE INSPECTION BASED ON FULL-FIELD PULSE-ECHO ULTRASONIC WAVE PROPAGATION IMAGING

3.1 CFRP wing skin panel

A CFRP wing skin panel structure with barely visible impact damages (BVIDs) was inspected with full-field pulse-echo UPI system based on the experimental setup as shown in Fig. 3. Laser pulse energy was set to 4.85 mJ at stand-off distance of 1.434 m. The spatial scanning interval was 0.52 mm and pulse repetition rate (PRR) was set to 1000 Hz. Through-the-thickness ultrasounds were filtered using in-line band-pass at 1 – 3 MHz. The scan area of $312 \times 104 \text{ mm}^2$ on the CFRP wing skin panel of $1125 \times 500 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ including the impact damages and a PZT element (not a sensor but an additional mass) attached on back side was inspected.

Figure 3: CFRP wing skin panel with damages.

As results of inspection of scan area on the CFRP wing skin panel, full-field pulse-echo UWPI

video was generated based on full-field pulse-echo UWPI technique as shown in Fig. 4. Consequently, not only the two impact damages but also the PZT element on back side was visualized in the full-field pulse-echo UWPI freeze-frames, for example at 6.066 μ s.

Figure 4: Experimental result: full-field pulse-echo UWPI freeze frame snapshot at 6.066 μ s.

3.2 GFRP aircraft encoder case

A GFRP aircraft encoder case including artificial defects which are two drilled holes was inspected with full-field pulse-echo UPI system based on the experimental setup as shown in Fig. 5. Laser pulse energy was set to 3.5 mJ at stand-off distance of 1.434 m. The spatial scanning interval was 0.52 mm and PRR was set to 1000 Hz. Through-the-thickness ultrasounds were filtered using in-line band-pass and numerical filters at 20 – 200 kHz. As shown in Fig. 5a and 5b, the scan area of 247 \times 182 mm² on the GFRP aircraft encoder case was scanned.

Figure 5: Experimental setup of GFRP aircraft encoder case: (a) front side, and (b) back side.

As a result of scanning on the GFRP aircraft encoder case, full-field pulse-echo UWPI video was generated as shown in Fig. 6. Two drilled hole on back side of the GFRP aircraft encoder case were visualized in full-field pulse-echo UWPI freeze frame snapshot at 11.139 μ s. In addition, several defects which are invisible on surface of the specimen were visualized.

Figure 6: Experimental result: full-field pulse-echo UWPI freeze frame snapshot at 11.319 μ s.

3.3 PVC pipe structure

A PVC pipe structure which is curved was inspected with full-field pulse-echo UPI system based on the experimental setup as shown in Fig. 7. The erosion-type damage was included in the specimen which is 114 mm diameter. Laser pulse energy was set to 3.37 mJ at stand-off distance of 1.434 m. The scan area of $65 \times 104 \text{ mm}^2$ was scanned with spatial scanning interval of 0.52 mm and PRR of 1000 Hz. Acquired signals were filtered using in-line band-pass and numerical filters at 20 – 200 kHz.

Figure 7: Experimental setup of PVC pipe structure: (a) scan area, and (b) erosion-type damage in the specimen.

As results of inspection of the PVC pipe structure, pulse-echo UWPI freeze-frame was generated as shown in Fig. 8. Erosion-type damage inside the PVC pipe structure was visualized in pulse-echo UWPI freeze frame at 25.65 μ s even though the specimen was curved.

Figure 8: Experimental result: full-field pulse-echo UWPI freeze frame snapshot at 25.65 μs .

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, various composite structures which are a CFRP wing skin panel and a GFRP aircraft encoder case and a PVC pipe structure used in diverse industries were inspected using the developed full-field pulse-echo UWPI technique to visualize damages. The specimens were scanned using full-field pulse-echo UPI system based on generation and sensing lasers to generate and sense pulse-echo through-the-thickness ultrasound induced by laser excitation using thermoelastic mechanism. As results of the inspections, full-field pulse-echo UWPI videos were generated at each specimen inspection. BVIDs and an additional mass on back side in the CFRP wing skin panel were visualized in the full-field pulse-echo UWPI freeze frame snapshot at 6.066 μs . Artificial defects which are holes on back side in a GFRP aircraft encoder case were visualized in the full-field pulse-echo UWPI freeze frame snapshot at 11.319 μs . The erosion-type damage in PVC pipe structure which is curved structure was also visualized in the full-field pulse-echo UWPI freeze frame at 25.65 μs . Consequently, full-field pulse-echo UWPI imaging technique can visualize the damages in various composite structures using non-contact inspection method by generation and sensing lasers.

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